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RESEARCH ARTICLE

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Impact of Information Technology towards Culinary Business: A Case Study on Azizah Catering Pekalongan

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Abstract

Catering Business Management by Utilizing a Web-Based Information System. This study aims to facilitate the management of the catering business. The form and strategy of this research uses qualitative research methods with a descriptive approach through observation and interviews.

Based on the research that has been done, the researcher concludes that this web-based information system can help and facilitate the management of the Azizah catering business in running its business which was originally managed manually, can become automatic with the help of this system.

Keywords: Web-based information system, culinary business, and Azizah catering.

1 Introduction

In the modern era like today, business has become part of human survival, from small to large-scale businesses, from businesses that are managed personally to businesses that are managed in groups or teams (Marom et al., 2021). In addition to capacity and management, businesses also exist in various places according to their environment, which means that businesses are spread everywhere and run by anyone (Mahmud et al., 2020). For example, in Indonesia, according to the Central Statistics Agency (BPS), the number of micro, small and medium enterprises (MSMEs) has reached 64 million. The lift reached 99.9 percent of all businesses operating in Indonesia.

According to Griffin, R; Moorhead, (2016) business is an organization that provides goods or services with the intention of making a profit. If the needs of the community increase, then business institutions will also increase their development to meet these needs, while making a profit (Adinugraha et al., 2020).

One of the busiest businesses in Indonesia is the food catering business, where this catering business can be done without having to rent a place, it doesn't even require large capital like other businesses, because this catering business can be run at home and with relatively affordable capital when compared to other businesses or other forms of business (Hadikha et al., 2021). Catering itself in Indonesia has been widely spread in all regions, this catering business is generally a local business that only serves local markets that are easily accessible, Catering has emerged since the 1800s, but this type of business has only become popular since the 2000s, Catering is not something new among housewives in the village and in the city.

The word catering is taken from the verb cater, which means to prepare and serve food to the public, while others come from the word cater, which means people who serve food to the public (Fadholi et al., 2020). Catering is a business in the service sector in terms of providing or serving food requests for various purposes, catering is a type of food service where the place for cooking is different from the place where the food is served (Purwanto et al., 2020). Food is transported to another place to be served, for example to

a party, meeting, cafeteria or industrial cafeteria. The food served can be in the form of snacks, snacks or food baskets (Adinugraha & Nadhifah, 2020).

In this catering business, one of the most important things is the way it is managed, where the steps from start to finish must really be done according to the wishes of consumers, therefore this management system is sometimes not enough if it is done manually and requires digital assistance such as management with Web-Based Information System (Adinugraha & Muhtarom, 2021).

In this case, the focal point of the discussion will discuss how online information system facilities can be developed for managing the catering business. Catering businesses are generally local businesses that serve only local markets that are still easily accessible (Sholehuddin et al., 2021). One example is Azizah Catering, which comes from a home-based business, which relies a lot on word of mouth promotion from acquaintances or relatives who introduce them. Utilization of information systems that can be accessed online can improve customer service and even reach new customers so as to optimize business performance. This research focuses on solving problems for the catering business, with the development of an online catering business management information system.

2 Methods

This research was conducted based on the problems that exist in the marketing system of Azizah Catering. Where in accordance with the problems described in the introduction, data collection is needed in solving it. What is needed is a menu list which is usually referred to as a package list provided by Azizah Catering. Customer data that has become a permanent member and a price list for each product. The data collection method used is by conducting an interview system with the owner of Azizah Catering.

3 Result and discussion

With this web-based management system, catering management is easier and very helpful, because all the management has been arranged and scheduled in a neat and orderly manner, not as usual which has to be done manually in terms of recording expenditures, processing time, delivery hours, and total costs, and includes the calculation of turnover from income for one week to one month (Adinugraha et al., 2021).

Catering management in marketing is more focused on the right target market, making catering sharper in promoting. Compared to before, promotions were not organized and generalized even though they were in different places and environments, and this resulted in optimization in the azizah catering business (Musthofiyah et al., 2021).

The owner of azizah catering can also help more local people to work as admins of the azizah catering web system that has been developed. This can also be further developed and can open more job vacancies for the general public, which makes the unemployment rate in the surrounding area decrease, and of course this business will grow bigger and bigger (Lestari et al., 2021).

Bookkeeping such as expenditures for capital expenditures and so on are recorded accordingly by the system, even listed up to turnover and income. The process from its inception to completion on time starting from 06.00 WIB to 12.00 WIB, and with employees who have been assigned each one who makes the work completed quickly and neatly according to their duties.

Delivery of catering orders on time so as to give satisfaction to customers and can

make customers repeat orders. The following is an attachment for photo evidence of direct observation at Azizah Catering's business place.

Figure 1. The business process of Azizah Pekalongan's catering

Based on the results of interviews with the owner of Azizah Catering regarding the sales process so far, it can be explained in chart 1 below:

4 Conclusion

The conclusions obtained from the results of this study are as follows: this web-based information system will be able to handle the management in this Azizah Catreing business, this web-based information system can serve the needs of users in running their business, they can even manage data and customer needs and manage data on food ingredients and catering tools, it is easy to run its business because it has been arranged and regulated from the beginning from the promotion to the end of the finished order.

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